

Local Government in India

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Structure of Local Government

4.1. The Structure of Local Government in India: An Introduction

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The term *panchayati raj* in India signifies the system of rural self-government. It has been established in all the states of India by the acts of the state legislatures to build a grass root democracy in independent India. It is entrusted with the task of developing rural development in different sectors directly accountable to the district and sub-district level administration. It was constitutionally mandated as per the provisions of the 73rd Constitutional Amendment Act of 1992. The act provides for a three-tier system of *panchayati raj* in every state that has *gram panchayat* at the village level, *panchayat samiti* at the block level and *zilla parishad* at the district level. All the members of *panchayats* at the village, intermediate and the district level shall be elected directly by the people. Further, the chairperson of *panchayats* at the intermediate and district levels shall be elected indirectly by and from the elected members of the intermediate and district levels.

However, the chairperson of a *panchayat* at village level shall be elected in such a manner as the state legislature determines. The act provides for the reservation of seats for scheduled castes and scheduled tribes in every *panchayat* in proportion of their population to the total population in the *panchayat* area. The act provides for the reservation of not less than one third of seats for women. The act provides for a five-year term of office to the *panchayat* at every level.

The term urban local government in India signifies the governance of an urban area by the people through their elected representatives. There are eight types of urban local government in India. The urban local government provisions have been added in the 74th Amendment Act, 1992. The eight types are:

Municipal Corporations

Municipal corporations are created for the administration of big cities like Delhi, Mumbai, Kolkata, Hyderabad, Bangalore and others. They are established in the states by the acts of the concerned state legislatures, and in the union territories by the acts of the Parliament of India. A municipal corporation has three authorities, namely, the council, the standing committees and the commissioner.

The council is the deliberative and legislative wing of the corporation. It consists of the councilors, directly elected by the people, as well as a few nominated persons having knowledge or experience of municipal administration. The council is headed by a mayor. He is assisted by a deputy mayor. The standing committees are created to facilitate the working of the council, which is too large in size. They deal with public works, education, health, taxation,

finance and so on. They make decisions in their fields. The municipal commissioner is responsible for the implementation of the decisions taken by the council and its standing committees. Thus, he is the chief executive authority of the corporation appointed by the state government.

Municipality

The municipalities are established for the administration of towns and smaller cities. Like the corporations, they are also set up in the states by the acts of the concerned state legislatures and in the union territory by the acts of the Parliament of India. They are also known by various other names like municipal council, municipal committee, municipal board, borough municipality, city municipality and others.

Like a municipal corporation, a municipality also has three authorities, namely, the council, the standing committees and the chief executive officer. The council is the deliberative and legislative wing of the municipality. It consists of the councilors directly elected by the people. The council is headed by a president/chairman. He is assisted by a vice-president/vice-chairman and presides over the meetings of the council. The standing committees are created to facilitate the working of the council. They deal with public works, taxation, health, finance and so on. The chief executive officer/chief municipal officer is responsible for day-to-day general administration of the municipality. He is appointed by the state government.

Notified Area Committee

A notified area committee is created for the administration of two types of areas—a fast developing town due to industrialization, and a town which does not yet fulfill all the conditions necessary for the constitution of a municipality, but which otherwise is considered important by the state government. Since it is established by a notification in the government gazette, it is called a notified area committee. Though it functions within the framework of the State Municipal Act, only those provisions of the act apply to it which are notified in the government gazette by which it is created.

Its powers are almost equivalent to those of a municipality. But unlike the municipality, it is an entirely nominated body, that is, all the members of a notified area committee including the chairman are nominated by the state government. Thus, it is neither an elected body nor a statutory body.

Town Area Committee

A town area committee is set up for the administration of a small town. It is a semi-municipal authority and is entrusted with a limited number of civic functions like drainage, roads, street lighting, and conservancy. It is created by a separate act of a state legislature. Its composition,

functions and other matters are governed by the act. It may be wholly elected or wholly nominated by the state government or partly elected and partly nominated.

Cantonment Board

A cantonment area is a delimited area where the military forces and troops are permanently stationed. A cantonment board is established for municipal administration for civilian population in the cantonment area. It works under the administrative control of the Defense Ministry of the central government. A cantonment board consists of partly elected and partly nominated members.

The military officer commanding the station is the ex-officio president of the board and presides over its meetings. The vice-president of the board is elected by the elected members from amongst themselves for a term of five years. The sources of income include both tax revenue and non-tax revenue. The executive officer of the cantonment board is appointed by the President of India. He implements all the resolutions and decisions of the board and its committees.

Township

This type of urban government is established by the large public enterprises to provide civic amenities to its staff and workers who live in the housing colonies built near the plant. The enterprise appoints a town administrator to look after the administration of the township. He is assisted by some engineers and other technical and non-technical staff. Thus, the township form of urban government has no elected members. In fact, it is an extension of the bureaucratic structure of the enterprises.

Port Trust

The port trusts are established in the port areas like Mumbai, Kolkata, Chennai and so on for two purposes: (i) to manage and protect the ports; and (ii) to provide civic amenities. A port trust is created by an Act of Parliament. It consists of both elected and nominated members.

Special Purpose Agency

In addition to these seven area-based urban bodies (or multipurpose agencies), the states have set up certain agencies to undertake designated activities or specific functions that 'legitimately' belong to the domain of municipal corporations or municipalities or other local urban governments. In other words, these are function-based and not area-based. They are known as 'single purpose', 'uni-purpose' or 'special purpose' agencies or 'functional local bodies.' Some such bodies are:

- town improvement trusts;

- urban development authorities;
- water supply and sewerage boards;
- housing boards;
- pollution control boards;
- electricity supply boards;
- city transport boards.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

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